

Synthesis and antileishmanial activity of 1-aminomethyl-5-substituted-3-{4'-(3''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoylhydrazono}-2-indolinones

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Abstract : 5-Substituted-3-{4'-(3''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoylhydrazono}-2-indolinones (3-6) were synthesised by the condensation of 4-(3'-chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoylhydrazine (2) and 5-substituted isatins. Mannich reaction in the presence of formaldehyde and heterocyclic secondary amines in indolinones (3-6) furnished 1-aminomethyl-5-substituted-3-{4'-(3''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoylhydrazono}-2-indolinones (7-22). The structures of the compounds have been established by means of correct elemental analysis and spectral data (IR, PMR and Mass). The compounds have been screened for their antileishmanial potential against *Leishmania donovani*.

Keywords : Isatins, Mannich reaction, antileishmanial activity.

Introduction

Isatins and their derivatives constitute a class of biologically active heterocycles which have been found associated with antiviral¹, antibacterial², anthelmintic³, amoebicidal⁴, antifungal⁵, anti-HIV⁶, anticonvulsant⁷, antileukemic⁸, antifertility⁹, herbicidal¹⁰, antiinflammatory¹¹ and CNS depressant¹² activities. In addition to these cysticidal¹³ and hypotensive¹⁴ responses have also been reported in certain isatin derivatives. Substituted benzyloxy group is present in many broad spectrum antifungals¹⁵, local anesthetics¹⁶ and antileishmanial agents¹⁷. In the light of these observations it was considered of interest to synthesise 3-chlorobenzoyloxy substituted benzoic acid hydrazide incorporated isatins (Schiff's bases) and their Mannich bases.

Results and discussion

Methyl 4-hydroxybenzoate was treated with 3-chlorobenzyl chloride to get methyl 4-(3'-chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoate (1) which on hydrazinolysis gave 4-(3'-chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoylhydrazine (2). Acid catalysed condensation of 2 with 5-substituted isatins in equimolar proportion gave 5-substituted-3-{4'-(3''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoylhydrazono}-2-indolinones (3-

6). The required isatins were prepared by the standard method available in the literature¹⁸. Mannich condensation of 3-6 with heterocyclic secondary amines in the presence of formaldehyde gave 1-aminomethyl-5-substituted-3-{4'-(3''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoylhydrazono}-2-indolinones (7-22) (Scheme 1).

*Antileishmanial activity*¹⁹ :

Compounds 7-22 were tested for their antileishmanial activity against *Leishmania donovani*, causative agent of Kala-azar. Compounds 7, 10, 14, 18, 21 and 22 showed 50% inhibition of *L. donovani* while compounds 11, 15 and 19 exhibited 70-75% inhibition of *L. donovani*. Pentamidine was taken as standard drug.

Experimental

The melting points were taken in open capillaries in sulfuric acid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer IR spectrophotometer and PMR spectra on Bruker DRX-300 instrument using CDCl₃ as solvent. TMS was taken as internal standard. Chemical shifts are expressed in δ ppm. Mass spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu GC-MS Q P2010 instrument. Purity of the compounds was checked by

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Scheme 1

TLC silica gel G plates and spots were located by iodine vapours. The physical data of the compounds prepared are presented in Table 1.

Methyl 4-(3'-chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoate (1) :

A mixture of methyl 4-hydroxybenzoate (0.045 mol), 3-chlorobenzyl chloride (0.045 mol), anhyd. K₂CO₃ (7.1 g) in DMF (30 mL) was refluxed for 7-8 h and poured in the ice cold water. The solid thus obtained was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from *n*-propyl alcohol; IR (cm⁻¹) : 1723 (-CO-), 1252 (-CH₂O-), 749 (C-Cl).

4-(3'-Chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoylhydrazine (2) :

Compound 1 (0.01 mol), hydrazine hydrate 98% (1 ml) in *n*-propyl alcohol (50 mL) was refluxed for 15-16 h. Excess of solvent was distilled off and the solution was poured in ice cold water. The solid product thus obtained was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from *n*-propyl alcohol; IR (cm⁻¹) : 3440,

3301 (NH, NH₂), 1661 (-CO-), 1253 (-CH₂O-), 749 (C-Cl).

5-Substituted-3-{4'-(3''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoylhydrazono}-2-indolinones (3-6) : (General method) :

A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol) and 5-substituted isatins (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 mL) containing 3-4 drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed for half an hour and left overnight at room temperature. The solid product so obtained was washed with methanol; 3 IR (cm⁻¹) : 3424, 3194 (NH), 1669, 1609 (-CO-), 1250 (-CH₂O-), 749 (C-Cl); MS (*m/z*) : 405 (M⁺), 407 (M+2); 4 IR (cm⁻¹) : 3463, 3227 (NH), 1675, 1609 (-CO-), 1250 (-CH₂O-), 749 (C-Cl); MS (*m/z*) : 419 (M⁺), 421 (M+2); 5 IR (cm⁻¹) : 3463, 3224 (NH), 1669, 1607 (-CO-), 1253 (-CH₂O-), 756 (C-Cl), 550 (C-Br); 6 MS (*m/z*) : 439 (M⁺), 441 (M+2), 443 (M+4).

1-Aminomethyl-5-substituted-3-{4'-(3''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoylhydrazono}-2-indolinones (7-22) : (General method) :

5-Substituted-3-{4'-(3''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoylhydrazono}-2-indolinones (3-6) (0.005 mol) were suspended in minimum quantity of DMF. To this formaldehyde (0.5 ml, 37%) and amines (0.005 mol) were added with vigorous stirring. The solution was warmed for 2 min on a water bath and left overnight at room temperature. The solid product, thus obtained was filtered, dried and crystallised from chloroform : petroleum ether (60-80 °C) (1 : 1); 7 IR (cm⁻¹) : 3427 (NH), 2855 (>N-CH₂-N<), 1679, 1605 (-CO-), 1252 (-CH₂O-), 1135 (-CH₂O-CH₂-), 743 (C-Cl); PMR δ (ppm) : 2.63-2.66 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 3.69-3.72 (4H, t, -CH₂-O-CH₂-), 4.49 (2H, s, >N-CH-N<), 5.11 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 7.00-8.00 (13H, m, Ar-H including NH); MS (*m/z*) : 504 (M⁺), 506 (M+2); 8 PMR δ (ppm) : 1.42-1.59 (6H, m, -CH₂CH₂CH₂-), 2.55-2.58 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 4.47 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.12 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 7.01-8.00 (13H, m, Ar-H including NH); 9 PMR δ (ppm) : 2.04 (3H, s, N-Me), 2.27-2.47 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 2.52-2.62 (4H, t, -CH₂-N(Me)-CH₂-), 4.49 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.11 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 6.98-7.98 (13H, m, Ar-H including NH); MS (*m/z*) : 517 (M⁺), 519 (M+2); 10 IR (cm⁻¹) : 3427 (NH), 2853 (>N-CH₂-N<), 1679, 1605 (-CO-), 1252 (-CH₂O-), 749 (C-Cl); 11 PMR δ (ppm) : 2.71 (3H, s, Ar-Me), 2.63-2.65 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 3.69-3.72 (4H, t, -CH₂-O-CH₂-), 4.49 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.11 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 6.93-8.01 (12H, m, Ar-H including NH); 12 IR (cm⁻¹) : 3435 (NH), 2855 (>N-CH₂-N<),

Table 1. Characterisation data of the compounds prepared

Compd.	R ₁	R ₂	M.p. (°C)	Yield. (%)	Molecular formula	Elemental analysis (%) :		
						Found (Calcd.)		
						C	H	N
1	-	-	74-76	70	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₃ Cl	-	-	-
2	-	-	132-134	70	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	-	-	-
3	H	-	250-252	76	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	-	-	-
4	Me	-	254-256	72	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	-	-	-
5	Br	-	268-270	68	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₃ ClBr	-	-	-
6	Cl	-	>280	75	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₂	-	-	-
7	H	Morpholino	158-160	75	C ₂₇ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	64.19 (64.28)	4.90 (4.96)	11.01 (11.11)
8	H	Piperidino	122-124	75	C ₂₈ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	66.90 (66.93)	5.30 (5.37)	11.08 (11.15)
9	H	N-Me-Piperazino	146-148	68	C ₂₈ H ₂₈ O ₃ N ₅ Cl	64.90 (64.99)	5.36 (5.41)	13.48 (13.53)
10	H	Pyrrolidino	140-142	70	C ₂₇ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	66.32 (66.39)	5.09 (5.12)	11.39 (11.47)
11	Me	Morpholino	216-218	80	C ₂₈ H ₂₉ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	64.58 (64.61)	5.52 (5.57)	10.71 (10.78)
12	Me	Piperidino	216-218	70	C ₂₈ H ₂₉ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	66.60 (66.66)	5.71 (5.75)	10.71 (10.76)
13	Me	N-Me-Piperazino	206-208	76	C ₂₉ H ₃₀ O ₃ N ₅ Cl	65.49 (65.53)	5.60 (5.64)	13.02 (13.08)
14	Me	Pyrrolidino	172-174	76	C ₂₈ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	66.90 (66.93)	5.31 (5.37)	11.02 (11.09)
15	Br	Morpholino	220-222	70	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₄ ClBr	55.52 (55.57)	4.01 (4.10)	9.43 (9.50)
16	Br	Piperidino	214(d)	70	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₄ ClBr	57.80 (57.83)	4.41 (4.47)	9.46 (9.50)
17	Br	N-Me-Piperazino	160-162	60	C ₂₈ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₅ ClBr	56.32 (56.37)	4.50 (4.53)	11.60 (11.66)
18	Br	Pyrrolidino	178-180	65	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₅ ClBr	55.72 (55.76)	4.09 (4.13)	9.72 (9.80)
19	Cl	Morpholino	214-216	80	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₄ Cl ₂	60.18 (60.22)	4.41 (4.46)	10.60 (10.66)
20	Cl	Piperidino	206-208	80	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₂	62.64 (62.68)	4.81 (4.85)	10.30 (10.40)
21	Cl	N-Me-Piperazino	158-160	70	C ₂₈ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₅ Cl ₂	60.86 (60.98)	4.87 (4.90)	12.60 (12.70)
22	Cl	Pyrrolidino	196-198	76	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₂	60.01 (60.06)	4.54 (4.59)	10.60 (10.66)

1679, 1605 (-CO-), 1253 (-CH₂O-), 743 (C-Cl); MS (*m/z*) : 504 (M⁺), 506 (M+2); **14** PMR δ (ppm) : 1.25-1.42 (4H, m, -CH₂CH₂-), 2.17-2.27 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 4.49 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.12 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 6.91-8.01 (12H, m, Ar-H including NH); MS (*m/z*) : 502 (M⁺), 504 (M+2); **16** IR (cm⁻¹) : 3435 (NH), 2854 (>N-CH₂-N<), 1675, 1603 (-CO-), 1253 (-CH₂O-), 748 (C-Cl), 550 (C-Br); PMR

δ (ppm) : 1.42-1.61 (6H, m, -CH₂CH₂CH₂-), 2.55-2.58 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 4.47 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.12 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 6.96-7.98 (12H, m, including NH); **19** MS (*m/z*) : 538 (M⁺), 540 (M+2), 542 (M+4); **20** PMR δ (ppm) : 1.56-1.61 (6H, m, -CH₂CH₂CH₂-), 2.50-2.58 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 4.47 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.12 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 7.05-7.50 (12H, m, Ar-H, including NH); **22** IR

(cm^{-1}) : 3437 (NH), 2855 ($>\text{N}-\text{CH}_2-\text{N}<$), 1675, 1609 (-CO-), 1253 ($-\text{CH}_2\text{O}-$), 748 (C-Cl); MS (m/z) : 522 (M^+), 524 ($\text{M}+2$).

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